

Circular economy and life cycle assessment of alumina production: Simulation-based comparison of Pedersen and Bayer processes

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ABSTRACT

The excessive production of bauxite residue (red mud) in the Bayer process is one of the major challenges amongst alumina producers. The Pedersen process is known as a combination of smelting reduction of bauxite and leaching treatment of the produced slag for alumina production, and the process also produces an inert bauxite residue (grey mud), which is more suitable for further processing compared to the red mud. This paper describes the life cycle assessment for two alumina production processes, the current commercialized Bayer process and the alternative Pedersen process, based on the complete mass and energy balance simulation. Process simulation and environmental software are applied to quantify the metallurgical processes and their related environmental effects. By assuming the same treatments for the bauxite residues, it is found that, with the production of pig iron, the Pedersen process shows the best performance in mineral resource scarcity but requires a higher energy demand and generates twice the amount of bauxite residue compared to the Bayer process. The final, relative performance in climate change impact depends on the carbon intensity of energy and the bauxite ore composition.

1. Motivation and background

Resource efficiency and transition to circular economy is essential to develop a sustainable, resource-smart, low-carbon and competitive Europe (European Commission, 2019). In the past few decades, the global material demand has increased fourfold, driven by a doubling in both population numbers and our material demand per capita, as a result of the growing middle-class in the developing countries (Oberle et al., 2019; Schandl et al., 2018). As the world's largest net importer of resources, resource utilization is vital for the European economy, potentially also leading to large savings for its industry (INNOVA, 2012). Increased resource utilization in primary production will reduce climate and ecosystem biodiversity impacts from metal demand, where mining and metal refining are important contributors globally (Oberle et al., 2019).

Iron and aluminium represent the largest and second largest metal flows globally from primary extraction, in quantity and value. While metals are highly useful for our society, their production also generates byproducts and environmental concerns, i.e. in alumina production volumes of bauxite residue, or 'red mud'. The global metallurgical grade alumina production is 124 million tonnes in the year 2019, with around

8.5 million tonnes produced in Europe (World Aluminium, 2020). More than 95% of the alumina produced around the world derives from bauxite ore by the established 'Bayer process' (World Aluminium, 2015), where alumina is extracted from bauxite ore with sodium hydroxide solution in digesters (Zhu et al., 2020). The produced slurry from the digesters contains dissolved sodium aluminate and a solid bauxite residue. The global inventory of Bayer bauxite residue (B-BR) landfilled is estimated to be more than 2.7 billion tonnes, with an annual growth rate of over 120 million tonnes (Klauber et al., 2009), close to the annual global primary aluminium production. Bauxite residue from the Bayer process contains not only alkaline materials, such as NaOH and Na₂SiO₃, left over from the solution phase (Wang et al., 2018), but also significant quantities of valuable resources: around 30–50 wt% iron oxide and 15–25 wt% residual aluminum oxide (Safarian and Kolbeinsen, 2016b). Thus around 36–60 million tonnes iron oxide and 18–30 million tonnes aluminum oxide are wasted in bauxite residue annually. The treatment of bauxite residue represents 1–3% of the total alumina production cost, varying from 4 to 12 USD per tonne (Evans, 2015), and the various landfilling treatments also carry significant environmental risks (Barbhuiya et al., 2011; Burke et al., 2012; Evans, 2016; He et al., 2013; Ruyters et al., 2011). B-BR has currently limited options for

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valorization (Balomenos et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2014; Safarian and Kolbeinsen, 2016a). Considering the annual production rate, it is one of the largest global final industrial waste flows (World Aluminium, 2015).

A promising alternative process to produce alumina from bauxite ore is the 'Pedersen process', which was operated commercially in Norway and several places in the world until the middle of the 20th century when rising energy costs caused a shift to the less energy-intensive Bayer process (Miller and Irgens, 2016; Safarian and Kolbeinsen, 2016a). The Pedersen process involves a combination of pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical processes to extract pig iron and alumina from bauxite, yielding a residual 'grey mud' (Pedersen, 1927; Safarian and Kolbeinsen, 2016a). As the Pedersen process converts both the aluminium and iron from bauxite into product, it should lead to natural resource conservation (Pauliuk, 2018) and appear more in line with a circular economy paradigm when compared to the Bayer process. Moreover, mainly due to the absence of iron and its lower alkalinity compared to the Bayer bauxite residue, the Pedersen bauxite residue (P-BR)/grey mud is generally considered less harmful and better suited for valorization than conventional bauxite residue (Azof et al., 2020; Safarian and Kolbeinsen, 2016a, b; Vafeias et al., 2018).

Currently, the Pedersen process is gaining renewed interest and research is conducted at experimental and/or pilot scale to improve the process. While the Pedersen process may be considered in development, the Bayer process is operated commercially in a highly integrated and optimized manner with more than a century's development time. To our knowledge, there is no published environmental comparison between the Bayer and the Pedersen process in a life cycle perspective.

The main objective of this study is to apply an environmental system-level comparison of Pedersen and Bayer processes for production of metallurgical grade alumina. The comparison is conducted by linking material and energy characteristics and thermodynamic simulations on process level with life cycle environmental impacts and resource efficiency indicators. Use of simulation tools allows for consistent comparison even if the Bayer and Pedersen process are at highly different maturities, and to cover for gaps in empirical data at industrial scale for the Pedersen process. Our main aim is to identify the conditions that lead to preference for either process, for selected environmental and circular economy indicators. The assessment informs further process development particularly for the Pedersen process, as well as highlight policy aspects for circular economy in the aluminium production.

2. Methods

2.1. Model architecture

From a circular economy perspective, with considering the environmental impact, energetic quality and economic impact, the modelling approach to evaluate the life cycle performance of the process alternatives covers thermodynamic process simulation and life cycle assessment (LCA) tools supported by experimental data, thermodynamic factors, and literature data for direct emissions. The general model architecture is shown in Fig. 1.

Metallurgical process simulation allows rigorous validation of metallurgical processes, considering thermodynamics and mass balance for major flows (Gediga, 2014). Several publications apply simulation tools and digitization to investigate the life cycle environmental aspects of metallurgical processes (Bartie et al., 2020; Elomaa et al., 2020; Reuter et al., 2018; Reuter and van Schaik, 2015; Reuter et al., 2015; Scheidema et al., 2016), and in most cases HSC SIM is used for the simulation (HSC software, 2020). In the present study, HSC SIM was used for the modelling of both Pedersen process and Bayer process alike to ensure comparability and control of process factors, and the simulation outputs from the core for our environmental LCA. Direct emissions vary with process conditions and operations, and with lack of empirical data, standard emission factors were used for the calculation of the direct emissions. The final inventories were compiled as an integrated

Fig. 1. Various tools and methods integrated for the analyses.

system using LCA software, including connected processes and value chains to allow simulation of scenarios and process optimization in respect to the energy demand, resource uptake, and exergy efficiency (Reuter, 2016).

2.2. General process descriptions

The primary raw material for alumina production process is bauxite ore. Bauxite is a naturally occurring heterogeneous material and composed of one or more aluminum hydroxide minerals, including primarily gibbsite $[\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3]$, boehmite $[\gamma\text{-AlO}(\text{OH})]$ and diaspore $[\alpha\text{-AlO}(\text{OH})]$ (The Clay Minerals Society (CMS) Nomenclature Committee, 2016; Petrakis et al., 2020). There are also other compounds in bauxite, such as hematite $[\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3]$, goethite $[\text{FeO}(\text{OH})]$, quartz $[\text{SiO}_2]$, rutile/anatase $[\text{TiO}_2]$, kaolinite $[\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4]$ and other impurities in minor or trace quantities (Verma et al., 2017). The operating parameters (e.g. temperature and pressure) of the Bayer process are highly dependent on bauxite's chemical and mineralogical composition (Jones and Haynes, 2011). Diaspore is more difficult to be solved in sodium hydroxide solution than gibbsite or boehmite, therefore requires higher energy inputs in the Bayer production process (Jones and Haynes, 2011). Bauxite with an $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ mass ratio <6.25 or with a reactive silica content higher than 8 wt% is regarded as low-grade ore (Smith, 2009), which needs a further desilication treatment due to the silicon-bearing phases. This typical bauxite is not favorable for both the Bayer and the Pedersen process (Azof et al., 2020). The chemical composition of bauxites for that were taken from several locations in the world are presented in Table 1.

In our case, the process models enable the calculation of the inventory while varying the composition of the bauxite and the comparison of life cycle indicators for the two production processes accordingly. The bauxite ore compositions used in the current study are listed in Table 2, a typical hypothetical composition of bauxite ore is considered, from high-grade bauxite ore B18.5 to low-grade bauxite ore B30, only the diaspore $[\alpha\text{-AlO}(\text{OH})]$ and Fe_2O_3 compositions vary, since these two are the raw material sources for the products - alumina and pig iron.

Life cycle inventories for industrially operated Bayer process are available in one of the European Aluminium Association reports (European Aluminium Association, 2013). For the need of consistency in the comparison, the theoretical material and energy balances extracted from the simulation were used. The flowsheets for both Bayer process and Pedersen process are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 separately, with process parameter settings listed in Table 3 and Table 4 accordingly. Input and output flows for individual unit operations are shown in the two figures, and the corresponding values of flows in each unit operation can also be read through flowsheet report option in HSC SIM, used as basis for inventories in the LCA.

To simplify the task, the simulation omits certain stages in the processes which leads to a slight underestimation of the energy use. This

Table 1
Chemical composition of bauxites at several locations in the world.

NO.	Country, location	Composition (wt%)					Aluminium-minerals
		Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	LOI	
1	Brazil, Trombetas (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	51.8	5.1	13.9	1.2	28.0	Mainly gibbsite, <1 wt% boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
2	Guinea, Friguia (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	49.5	6.2	14.3	1.6	28.4	Mainly gibbsite (Patterson, 1967)
3	Greece, Parnassos-Ghiona (Laskou et al., 2010)	62.5	2.1	19.5	2.9	13.0	Mainly diaspore (Patterson, 1967)
4	Ghana, Awaso (Patterson, 1967)	51.6	1.3	17.4	1.9	27.8	Mainly gibbsite, about 9 wt% of total is boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
5	Australia, Gove (Patterson, 1967)	50.0	4.0	17.1	3.4	26.4	Mainly gibbsite, minor boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
6	Jamaica, Clarendon (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	49.0	2.7	18.0	2.4	28.0	Mainly gibbsite, 7-10 wt% boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
7	Iran, Sar-Faryab (Zarasvandi et al., 2008)	52.5	6.4	19.7	3.3	18.1	Mainly diaspore (Zarasvandi et al., 2008)
8	India, Orissa (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	47.7	2.8	23.2	1.1	25.1	Mainly gibbsite, minor boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
9	Guinea, Boke (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	56	1.5	7.9	3.7	30.1	Mainly gibbsite, 4-5 wt% boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
10	Australia, Weipa (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	58	4.5	6.9	2.5	26.8	Mainly gibbsite, 4 wt % boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
11	Guyana, Mackenzie (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	59	4.9	2.9	2.4	30.4	Up to 95 wt% of gibbsite, minor boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
12	Australia, Darling Range (L. Keith Hudson et al., 2000)	37	26.5	16.4	1.1	19.3	Mainly gibbsite, minor boehmite (Patterson, 1967)
13	China, Shanxi (Liu et al., 2009)	62.4	11.6	5.8	NA	NA	Mainly diaspore (Liu et al., 2009)
14	China, Henan (Liu et al., 2009)	65.3	11.8	3.4	NA	NA	Mainly diaspore (Liu et al., 2009)

Table 2
Bauxite ores employed in the modelling, in order of increasing Fe content.

Components	Bauxite B18.5	Bauxite B21.5 ^a	Bauxite B24	Bauxite B27	Bauxite B30
α-AlO(OH)	73.2	70.2	67.7	64.7	61.7
Fe ₂ O ₃	18.5	21.5	24	27	30
SiO ₂	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
TiO ₂	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7
CaCO ₃	3.1	3.1	3.1	3.1	3.1
Total	100	100	100	100	100

^a Baseline bauxite in HSC SIM modelling.

requires energy requirements for ‘transportation’ and ‘filtration’ included in the flowsheets, as well as preparation of bauxite ore (particle size treatment by crushing/milling). Energy losses during reactions and filtrations are also not included. The energy consumption in the omitted processes is of minor importance to the overall energy consumption, and to a large extent are also similar for both Bayer and Pedersen processes.

2.3. The Bayer process

The Bayer process simulation is based on the modelling of selected and defined unit processes and input-output parameters from the published literatures, described in the following section. In the Bayer process simulation, the bauxite ore, extraction liquor and lime addition are mixed and heated in digesters in the pressure leaching step. The pressure leaching process removes hydrated alumina from other insoluble oxides by reacting it with sodium hydroxide:

The alumina recovery rate in this process is assumed to be 85% (Balomenos et al., 2011). The produced hot slurry is then cooled for clarification. Clarification involves separation of the bauxite residue solids from the pregnant liquid solution, which consists of supersaturated NaAl(OH)₄ dissolved in NaOH solution. The NaAl(OH)₄-rich solution is then crystallized as Al(OH)₃ in the crystallization process:

The precipitated trihydrate crystals are filtered, washed, and calcined to convert the trihydrate to alumina (Al₂O₃) through Filtration, Rotary kiln and Calcination processes, as shown in Equation (3). The spent liquor is returned to digestion to pick up more alumina, the recovery process is not shown in Fig. 2, but employed in life cycle inventory directly.

2.4. The Pedersen process

Most of the data that are employed to build the Pedersen process in HSC Sim were obtained from laboratory experiments and pilot tests, in addition with some published data and some estimated data by FactSage (Factsage, 2020) thermodynamic calculations and skilled researchers. The process combines pyro- and hydrometallurgical processes. Since bauxite contains primarily hydrous aluminum oxides, often mixes with iron oxyhydroxides, kaolinite, and small amounts of anatase (TiO₂) (The Clay Minerals Society (CMS) Nomenclature Committee, 2016), the calcination of raw bauxite before the smelting part is considered. The decomposition of hydrates and the decomposition of calcium carbonate happen in the same step:

Fig. 2. HSC simulation for the Bayer process.

The calcined bauxite is fed into the electric arc furnace (EAF). In the smelting process, calcined bauxite is smelted with lime as the flux and partially reduced by coke, which yields pig iron due to the carbothermic reduction of the iron oxides to metallic iron, and a calcium-aluminate slag. The amount of the lime is adjusted in order to form leachable calcium-aluminate phases in the slag. According to the literature (Azof et al., 2017; Blake et al., 1967), the leachable calcium-aluminate phases in sodium carbonate solutions are $12\text{CaO}\cdot 7\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ phase (mayenite) and monocalcium aluminate $\text{CaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, while the presence of $3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CaO}\cdot 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and calcium-aluminium-silicate phases hinders the leaching process. In the needs of simplicity, the following reactions are considered:

The Boudouard reaction should also be considered in the EAF furnace:

The off-gas exiting the EAF furnace contains mainly $\text{CO}(\text{g})$ and $\text{CO}_2(\text{g})$, and is driven to the Energy recovery system - a post-combustion chamber, where the off-gas is combusted, and the energy is recovered (Odenthal et al., 2018). The combusted off-gas is composed of mainly $\text{CO}_2(\text{g})$, which can be collected and reused in the precipitation step.

Pig iron can be sold as a product, while calcium-aluminate slag is furtherly processed to the hydrometallurgical leaching process by using the sodium carbonate solution, where aluminium species are obtained in the pregnant liquid solution, while an insoluble residue P-BR is also formed:

The produced slurry from the leaching reactor is then filtered, where

grey mud is furtherly washed and the pregnant liquid solution is transferred to the precipitation process. The precipitation of aluminum hydroxide from the pregnant liquid solution takes place through carbon dioxide injection, which yields a sodium carbonate solution, and it is recirculated in the digestion step. The reactions considered for the precipitation process are as follows:

The alumina recovery rate in this process is assumed to be 90%, based on the laboratory experiment results. The precipitated trihydrate crystals are also filtered, washed, dewatered and calcined to convert the trihydrate to alumina (Al_2O_3) through Filtration 2, Rotary kiln and Calcination processes, which are the same as Bayer process. The gibbsite calcination reaction is:

The recirculation of off-gas and collected energy from Energy recovery system, and recycling process of soda solution after the precipitation step are not shown in Fig. 3, but are directly included in life cycle inventory.

2.5. Life cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment (LCA) can be used to evaluate the environmental impact of a product/process during its lifetime from raw material to end-of-life stage. It is carried out according to the best practices and framework described by ISO 14040 (Standardization, 2006a) and ISO 14044 (Standardization, 2006b) standards.

A challenging issue in LCA is the selection of methods to allocate the environmental burden of a specific production system between products and co-products. System expansion is a method used to avoid co-product allocation for systems with more than one product. The ISO standard

Fig. 3. HSC simulation for the Pedersen process.

recommends avoiding partitioning/allocation of the system by instead “expanding the product system to include the additional functions related to the co-products” (Standardization, 2006b). System expansion allows comparison of multifunctional systems and are of particular relevance for assessing utilization of residual flows (Hanssen and Huijbregts, 2019). The functional unit in this study is *one ton of alumina produced at gate*. The analysis includes benefits from co-production of pig iron in the Pedersen process by system expansion. The system boundaries for life cycle assessment are shown in Fig. 4 for (a) Bayer and (b) Pedersen processes.

EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2019 (European Environment Agency, 2019a, b; European Environment Agency, 2019) was used to estimate selected direct priority air emissions: for particulate matter (TSP, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) from ‘Calcination’ using emission factors for ‘Lime production’ scaled with feed input, for particulates, NO_x and SO_x from ‘Smelting reduction’ using emission factors for ‘Pig iron production’ scaled with pig iron production. The final LCI data were compiled using Simapro 9.3 software (Simapro, 2020) and the Ecoinvent v3.5 database (Wernet et al., 2016) for the background data.

The differences between the Pedersen and Bayer processes concern input material, energy consumption and products, and deserves a wide approach to environmental impacts and resource indicators. Damage-oriented (endpoint) indicators are useful to evaluate the potential net damages to human health, ecosystems and resources. Indicators on the level of impact categories, i.e., midpoint indicators, provide a better insight into the impact tradeoffs introduced by the two alternatives. For

the purpose of consistency, the lack of metal leaching potentials from management of bauxite residue from the Pedersen process, ecotoxicity and human non-carcinogenic impacts are excluded in this study, both on endpoint damage and midpoint levels. The water-energy nexus is highlighted by the European Union (Magagna D. et al., 2019) and a natural extension is consideration of resource depletion and climate (Brouwer et al., 2018). The underlying concept of the *nexus* is to understand, and thus quantify, interconnections between the various aspects of circular economy (Del Borghi et al., 2020; Pauliuk, 2018). The Pedersen process promises a better utilization of the mineral resources in bauxite, making mineral resource depletion a relevant aspect in the nexus. With the EU zero-waste policy in mind, we include the amount of solid waste to landfill as a separate indicator. Waste in landfills will have a considerably long-lasting impact on the environment (Obersteiner et al., 2007). From this, the environmental impacts are assessed using several impacts methods:

- Damage-oriented categories: Human health, Ecosystems and Resources excluding ecotoxic and human non-carcinogenic impacts; Recipe v1.03 Endpoints (H).
- Selected midpoint indicators to illustrate trade-offs, including particularly climate change emissions, mineral depletion and water consumption; Recipe v1.03 Midpoints (H).
- Cumulative energy demand (CED) v1.11 as compact indicator for energy use (Althaus et al., 2007).
- Solid waste to landfill (ton).

Table 3

The parameters used in the simulation of the Bayer process.

Unit process	Parameter	Value	Reference
Pressure leaching	Alumina recovery rate	85%	Balomenos et al. (2011)
	Hot slurry temperature	260 °C	Ma et al. (2009)
	Process pressure	50 bar	Ma et al. (2009)
	Lime addition	5 wt% of bauxite ore	Pan et al. (2015)
	Extraction liquor Na ₂ O	140 g/L	Wargalla and Brandt (2016)
Cooling step	Cooled slurry temperature	100 °C	Jones and Haynes (2011)
Clarification	Red mud moisture	40%	Hyeok-Jung et al. (2018)
	Filtration efficiency	95%	Scandrett (2016)
	Washing water amount	1 m ³ /t solids	Thomson and McLeod (1949)
Crystallization	Crystallization temperature	60 °C	Balomenos et al. (2011)
Filtration	Filtration cake moisture	25%	Petersen et al. (2016)
	Filtration efficiency	95%	Scandrett (2016)
	Washing water amount	1 m ³ /t solids	Thomson and McLeod (1949)
Rotary kiln	Output moisture of the precipitates	8%	Klett et al. (2016)
	Calciner temperature	105 °C	Assumption
Calcination	Calciner temperature	1100 °C	Balomenos et al. (2011)
	Off-gas temperature	900 °C	Assumption

Long-term management of mineral waste landfills is a major risk for stakeholders (Evans, 2016), and concerns related to safe management of BR may be considered a major motivation to shift to the Pedersen process (Miller and Irgens, 2016). However, in lack of better information concerning the remaining residual minerals, both B-BR and P-BR were assumed to undergo the same management and are therefore represented using the same BR management inventory. Arguably, this simplification and the exclusion of metal leaching and its potential toxicity impacts reduces the robustness in some of the findings (Jones and Haynes, 2011; Verma et al., 2017). We will revert to this point in our discussion of results.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Life cycle inventory

By integrating the direct emission data, and the mass balance and energy balance from the HSC Sim simulation model, the inventory data for both Pedersen process and Bayer process is produced. The LCI for these two processes are listed in Table 5 and Table 6 separately.

Looking across Tables 5 and 6, we make some insights into the characteristics of the two process options. As expected, increasing the iron content of the bauxite ore increases the demand for ore to produce 1 ton alumina, while simultaneously allowing for more pig iron to be produced in the Pedersen process. We may also note that the direct energy demand is higher in the Pedersen process, which is due to bauxite calcination and smelting reduction for the purpose of pig iron production.

Further, in both process the spent liquor/caustic soda solution is designed to be recycled and reused in the leaching process, and a large part of the leaching agents is being recirculated in the process. Considering the water recirculation, the Pedersen process still consumes almost twice the amount of water compared to the Bayer process. Significant amount of water exits with the Pedersen bauxite residue. The amount of P-BR generated per ton alumina is much higher than that of B-BR, since large amount of lime is added to produce the calcium-aluminate slag in the Pedersen process, and ends up in the bauxite residue.

Table 4

The parameters used in the simulation of the Pedersen process.

Unit process	Parameter	Value	Reference
Bauxite calcination	Calcination temperature	900 °C	Lab-scale experiments
	Off-gas temperature	600 °C	Assumption
Transportation	Temperature drop	100 °C	Sensor
	Amount of lime	Calculated based on experimental value	Azof et al. (2019)
Smelting reduction	Amount of coke	Control option for carbon balance	
	EAF temperature	1600 °C	Pilot scale experiments
	Calcium aluminate slag temperature	1600 °C	Pilot scale experiments
	Pig iron temperature	1500 °C	Pilot scale experiments
	Off-gas temperature	900 °C	Pilot scale experiments
	Off-gas composition	40% CO and 60% CO ₂	Pilot scale experiments
Energy recovery system	Pig iron composition	4.6%C, 1% Si and 94.4% Fe	FactSage calculation
	Output temperature of off-gas, after post-combustion	200 °C	Assumption
Natural cooling	Output product temperature	90 °C	Assume the same as leaching temperature
Leaching reactor	Leaching solution Na ₂ CO ₃	60 g/L	Mwase and Safarian (2020)
Filtration 1	Grey mud moisture	40%	Hyeok-Jung et al. (2018)
	Filtration efficiency	95%	Scandrett (2016)
	Washing water amount	1 m ³ /t solids	Thomson and McLeod (1949)
Precipitation	Reaction temperature	80 °C	lab-scale experiments
	Alumina recovery rate	90%	Assumptions
Filtration 2	Filtration cake moisture	25%	Petersen et al. (2016)
	Filtration efficiency	95%	Scandrett (2016)
	Washing water amount	1 m ³ /t solids	Thomson and McLeod (1949)
Rotary kiln	Output moisture of the precipitates	8%	Klett et al. (2016)
	Calciner temperature	105 °C	Assumption
Calcination of alumina hydrates	Calciner temperature	1100 °C	Balomenos et al. (2011)
	Off-gas temperature	900 °C	Assumption

In order to keep the comparison consistent, we employ the same electricity and heat in the Ecoinvent database for both processes. The European electricity inventory 'Electricity, medium voltage (RER) market for | APOS, U' and the Norwegian electricity inventory 'Electricity, medium voltage (NO), market for | APOS, U' are both employed in the life cycle assessment. The heat inventory 'Heat, from steam, in chemical industry market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry | APOS, U' is elected for both the processes, and this heat inventory is modelled for Europe. The European electricity dataset is grouped from a set of electricity data from European countries, with the electricity generated from many different resources, for example, hard coal, lignite, nuclear, natural gas and wind. Meanwhile, the Norwegian electricity dataset is modelled for Norway, almost exclusively comprising of hydropower. These two inventories were selected with respect to the electricity decarbonization policy, where electricity source is shifting from fossil fuel to renewable sources, for example, hydropower.

Fig. 4. System boundaries for life cycle assessment and energy analysis of both (a) Bayer and (b) Pedersen processes.

3.2. Life cycle contributions

Bauxite ore with 21.5 wt% Fe_2O_3 (B21.5) is used as baseline for the modelling. Contribution analysis and benchmark for midpoint indicators under the use of European electricity inventory is shown in Fig. 5, indicating that the preference for either of the alternatives depends on relative priority of the individual impacts. Net impact indicators with characterization numbers and normalization numbers are also listed in Table 7. Mining and extraction of bauxite ore contributes to most of the emission factors, most notably to ozone formation, particulate matter formation, terrestrial acidification and mineral resource scarcity. Although Pedersen process consumes twice amount of water compared to the Bayer process, the differences in their contribution to the 'water consumption' indicator are smaller, due to the fact that electricity is the major contributor to water consumption, and the water intensive processes of sodium hydroxide production (relevant for Bayer) and sodium carbonate production (relevant for Pedersen). The energy inputs electricity and heat contribute significantly to almost all the impact indicators except mineral resource scarcity. The use of coke and lime contributes insignificantly to the indicators.

Under the given assumptions, the Bayer process clearly shows the best performance for climate change, about 30% reduction compared to the Pedersen process, while the Pedersen has notable benefits for mineral scarcity –mainly attributable to the coproduction of pig iron. As outlined in Table 7, there are several impact categories with only a minor difference in life cycle impacts, and with the final comparison

depending on contributions from the system expansion. The benefits by iron coproduction in the Pedersen process is significant in contribution to climate change, particulate matter, ozone formation and mineral resource scarcity, leading to Pedersen being preferred for the latter three.

A main finding is the importance of leaching agents in both processes. The production of leaching agents, the sodium hydroxide for Bayer, and the sodium carbonate for Pedersen, is a major impact driver. And we could also see that sodium carbonate contributes to marine eutrophication indicator eighteen times higher than sodium hydroxide. Moreover, carbon dioxide used in precipitation in Pedersen process contributes significantly to several impacts, since CO_2 consumption in the precipitation exceeds the production of direct CO_2 emissions from the EAF. Water inputs and direct emissions are not insignificant, but relative performance of either process is closely dependent of the recirculation of the spent liquor and CO_2 . In the inventory, we are assuming all the spent liquor that exits the clarification/filtration step is recycled and returned to the process. Recirculation of spent liquor is current practice in industry, leading to economic as well as environmental savings, and is a requisite for environmental efficiency in the Pedersen process.

A major drawback of the Pedersen process is the electricity consumption in the smelting step to produce pig iron. To investigate the effect of expected decarbonization of heat and electricity supply in the future, Fig. 6 maps the global warming potential for each of the two processes as a function of energy decarbonization, for a variety of ore

Table 5
Life cycle inventory for Bayer process per functional unit of 1 ton of alumina.

Bayer process	Unit	Amount				
		Bauxite B18.5	Bauxite B21.5 *	Bauxite B24	Bauxite B27	Bauxite B30
Product						
Alumina	ton	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Pig iron	ton	0	0	0	0	0
Material input						
Bauxite ore	ton	2.05	2.15	2.26	2.40	2.53
NaOH	ton	0.88	0.88	0.90	0.91	0.92
Lime	ton	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.13
Fresh water used in Pressure leaching	ton	4.86	4.90	4.97	5.04	5.08
Fresh water for washing	ton	0.28	0.30	0.32	0.35	0.38
Energy input						
Energy input for Pressure leaching	kWh	1407.63	1423.74	1448.75	1475.79	1494.26
Energy input for Crystallization	kWh	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.59
Energy input for Rotary kiln	kWh	312.02	311.18	312.65	313.24	311.41
Energy input for Calcination	kWh	1149.29	1146.21	1151.61	1153.79	1147.06
Emissions to air						
Energy output 1 from Cooling step	kWh	927.54	938.43	955.16	973.31	985.84
Off gas 1 from Rotary kiln	ton	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35
Off gas 2 from Calcination	ton	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68
Direct emission, TSP	g	112	136	156	184	216
Direct emission, Particulates, < 10 um	g	56	68	78	92	108
Direct emission, Particulates, < 2.5 um	g	8.4	10.2	11.7	13.8	16.2
Emissions to water						
NaAl(OH) ₄ loss to Red mud wash water	ton	0.19	0.22	0.24	0.26	0.29
Na ₂ SiO ₃ loss to Red mud wash water	ton	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.01
NaOH loss to precipitates wash water	ton	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
Na ₂ SiO ₃ loss to precipitates wash water	ton	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
Waste to treatment						
B-BR/red mud (wet basis)	ton	1.43	1.59	1.75	1.96	2.17
Recirculated material						
Recirculated NaOH in spent liquor	ton	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.70
Recirculated water in spent liquor	ton	3.69	3.69	3.71	3.73	3.71
Recirculated Na ₂ SiO ₃ in spent liquor	ton	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04

grades. These results rely on a simplistic scenario changing the climate change intensity of direct energy consumption integrating European electricity inventory in the two processes for each of the five bauxites in Table 2 and keeping all other factors as they were. The results show that decarbonization of heat and electricity, relatively speaking, benefits the Pedersen process more, and the effect is increasing with the iron content. The production of pig iron, the reaction of CO₂ with the sodium aluminate hydroxide to form sodium carbonate in the precipitation, and the energy recovery system improve the climate competitiveness of the Pedersen process, with pig iron co-production to be the major contributor. Nonetheless, they indicate that ongoing changes in the energy supply systems work to benefit the Pedersen process.

3.3. Endpoint damage comparison

So far, we have discussed performance and preference for individual midpoint indicators, and the dependence for the comparison for climate change impacts towards energy supply. By selecting a decarbonized electricity inventory, i.e., the Norwegian electricity inventory, we present endpoint results in Fig. 7 for human health (a), ecosystems (b) and resources (c) for the five bauxites, in order to compare the processes on environmental damages. With these conditions, our comparison shows systematic preference for the Bayer process for human health damages and resource depletion. The results further indicate that relative benefits of the Bayer process are reduced when iron content increases. It is expected that the Bayer process will require more effort per ton alumina when the iron content of bauxite increases at the cost of bauxite ore, and this is apparent in the increasing trend of damages to human health, ecosystems and resources per ton alumina produced. Noteworthy, though, is that the Pedersen process shows the opposite trend, i.e., the coproduction of pig iron means that the overall endpoint damages per functional unit decrease with increasing iron content in bauxite ore.

If we look back to the results in Fig. 5, the relative benefits by the

Bayer process in health damages from reduced climate change, eutrophication and acidification out-weigh the higher impacts in particulate matter and ozone formation. Similarly, reduced mineral resource scarcity by the Pedersen process is considered less significant by the Recipe endpoint method than the increase in consumption of fossil resources and water. In terms of overall damages, Bayer process outperforms the Pedersen process in all the damage-oriented categories, except for the damage to the ecosystem for the two high iron bauxite cases B27 and B30.

3.4. Circular economy indicators

Climate, energy, and water are specific and often highlighted goals for the circular economy nexus, supplementary to resource efficiency (Brouwer et al., 2018; Magagna D. et al., 2019). These impacts are in parts covered by the damage-oriented endpoint indicators discussed previously, however; they also represent additional criteria for the circular economy. A suggested set of circular economy indicators is shown in Fig. 8, for comparison of the Pedersen and Bayer process routes for alumina production considering water consumption, cumulative energy demand, climate change, mineral resource depletion and solid waste generation. The results were carried out under conditions of both European electricity and Norwegian electricity, and the results provide a good basis for the further discussion of the two processes. The shift of electricity from European electricity to Norwegian electricity mainly affects the global warming indicator and cumulative energy demand indicator. One of the repeated findings in Fig. 8 is the systematic trend that higher iron content in bauxite would increase the impacts per ton alumina for the Bayer process with the opposite trend for Pedersen process. This effect is small for some of the indicators, but systematic across all indicators in Fig. 8.

Under the comparison of different electricity sources, the results show that for global warming emissions, the Bayer process is preferred

Table 6
Life cycle inventory for Pedersen process per functional unit of 1 ton of alumina.

Pedersen process	Unit	Amount				
		Bauxite B18.5	Bauxite B21.5*	Bauxite B24	Bauxite B27	Bauxite B30
Products						
Alumina	ton	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Pig iron (subtracted by system expansion)	ton	0.28	0.34	0.39	0.46	0.54
Material input						
Bauxite ore	ton	2.06	2.15	2.23	2.32	2.45
Lime	ton	1.23	1.23	1.23	1.23	1.23
Coke	kWh	612.04	739.94	854.91	998.58	1169.81
Sodium carbonate	ton	2.06	2.06	2.06	2.05	2.07
CO ₂	ton	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76
Fresh water for leaching	ton	34.30	34.34	34.36	34.18	34.43
Fresh water for washing	ton	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16
Air	ton	0.13	0.15	0.18	0.21	0.24
Energy input						
Energy input for bauxite calcination	kWh	858.66	879.92	898.62	917.34	950.23
Electricity for smelting reduction	kWh	1171.06	1229.44	1281.42	1340.93	1424.28
Energy input for Precipitation	kWh	1487.83	1490.05	1491.23	1483.67	1495.26
Energy input for Rotary kiln	kWh	313.97	314.17	314.34	312.65	314.98
Energy input for Calcination of alumina hydrates	kWh	1147.79	1149.16	1149.76	1143.53	1152.02
Emissions to the air						
Water vapor from Bauxite calcination	ton	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23
CO ₂ from Bauxite calcination	kg	28.08	29.31	30.40	31.62	33.40
Energy loss from transportation	kWh	58.11	60.34	60.31	64.49	67.74
Water vapor from Energy recovery system	kg	2.87	3.46	4.00	4.67	5.48
Nitrogen from Energy recovery system	kg	96.70	116.91	135.08	157.78	184.83
Energy loss from Natural cooling	kWh	1274.20	1295.50	1314.01	1329.96	1365.32
Water vapor from Rotary kiln	ton	0.35	0.36	0.36	0.35	0.36
Water vapor from Calcination of alumina hydrates	ton	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68
Energy output from leaching reactor	kWh	323.25	323.56	323.65	321.80	324.08
Direct emissions, TSP	g	238.00	289.00	331.50	391.00	459.00
Direct emissions, Particulates, < 10 μm	g	123.20	149.60	171.60	202.40	237.60
Direct emissions, Particulates, < 2.5 μm	g	23.80	28.90	33.15	39.10	45.90
Direct emissions, Nitrogen oxides	g	2.24	2.72	3.12	3.68	4.32
Direct emissions, Sulfur dioxide	g	10.64	12.92	14.82	17.48	20.52
Emissions to water						
NaOH loss to Grey mud wash water	kg	25.02	25.04	25.05	24.90	25.09
NaAl(OH) ₄ loss to Grey mud wash water	kg	110	110	110	110	110
NaAl(OH) ₄ loss to precipitates wash water	kg	3.60	3.60	3.60	3.60	3.60
Na ₂ CO ₃ loss to precipitates wash water	kg	25.66	25.67	25.66	25.49	25.65
Waste to treatment						
P-BR/grey mud (wet basis)	ton	3.89	3.91	3.92	3.90	3.95
Recirculated material & energy						
Recirculated water from soda solution	ton	31.76	31.80	31.81	31.64	31.87
Recirculated Na ₂ CO ₃ from soda solution	ton	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.79	1.80
Recirculated Na ₂ SiO ₃ from soda solution	ton	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Recirculated NaAl(OH) ₄ from soda solution	ton	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Recirculated CO ₂ from Energy recovery system	ton	0.20	0.24	0.28	0.33	0.39
Recirculated energy from energy recovery system	kWh	178.46	215.75	249.28	291.17	341.10

for ores high in aluminium oxide. The Pedersen process is preferred for climate change emissions for bauxites with high iron content when employing Norwegian electricity. Higher iron content corresponds to lower aluminium content, and for the Bayer process this means increasingly higher energy and material investments to extract the dwindling alumina yields. In contrast to the Bayer process, the Pedersen process can convert both the iron and aluminium oxides into products and should be better suited for high iron ores, which is interesting knowing that ores of up to 30 wt% iron oxides are currently used for alumina production [68].

Increasing the efficiency with which we use resources is a key-point under the concept of circular economy. The indicators included in Fig. 8 attributed at three separate types of (limited) resources: water, mineral resources, and energy. Even if they are interchangeable to some extent, i.e., energy and materials can be used to operate desalination, it is not apparent which one is more important within a circular economy. In the case we see that the Pedersen process has a lower mineral resource scarcity footprint, at the cost of higher water footprint and cumulative energy demand when compared to the Bayer process. There is thereby a clear trade of resource aspects, and one that is not answered by a shared endpoint method to aggregate these three resources.

Policies for circular economy in metals processing industry is closely connected to final waste volumes and may indeed be translated into minimizing waste production ([The European parliament and the council of the European Union, 2006](#)). In this perspective, it is interesting to see in Fig. 8 the Pedersen process is preferred for mineral resource scarcity due to the better utilization of mineral resources in the bauxite by coproduction of iron, while this occurs at the cost of increasing the total waste volumes for final management as the mineral residues generation is higher in the Pedersen process. Thereby the conclusions with regards to most resource efficient option is not unison and depends on aim, i.e. management of resources in the bauxite or the minimization of the volume to residual waste management. An additional perspective is potential extraction of remaining resources in the residual minerals, such as rare earth elements (REE). In view of REEs recovery, dissolution of REEs is associated with iron dissolution ([Borra et al., 2016](#)). Thereby, removal of iron from the bauxite residue would be beneficial and the Pedersen process would be preferred for the sequential recovery of REEs.

4. Summary and future work

The challenge in the simulation was the limited amount of available

Fig. 5. Midpoint LCA results for contribution analysis of Pedersen process and Bayer process with bauxite ore B21.5.

Table 7

Midpoint indicator results and normalized scores (World 2010) for Pedersen process and Bayer process with bauxite ore B21.5. The preferred process for each impact is marked in bold in the normalized results.

Impact category	Characterization numbers			Normalization numbers	
	Unit	Bayer	Pedersen	Bayer	Pedersen
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1648	2122	0.2063	0.2657
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	0.000985	0.00107	0.0164	0.0178
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq	626	838	1.3021	1.7435
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NOx eq	4.00	4.01	0.1943	0.1948
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM _{2.5} eq	2.89	2.81	0.1130	0.1097
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NO _x eq	4.04	3.99	0.2275	0.2244
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	7.15	8.47	0.1746	0.2067
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	1.86	2.92	2.8687	4.4921
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	0.10	0.36	0.0216	0.0786
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	92	57	0.0008	0.0005
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	433	652	0.4416	0.6650
Water consumption	m ³	28	37	0.1053	0.1389

industrial information for process operation, especially for the Pedersen process where published descriptions refer to laboratory scale. Most of the Pedersen process parameters are still under investigation, and energy integration potentials are difficult to validate. These are arguments for applying the simulation-based approach outlined in this paper, yet also indicative that some certain operational parameters might change for the Pedersen process when it is built in industrial scale, for example, the leaching parameters and Al recovery rate in the leaching step, filtration parameters, energy recovery method for the EAF off-gas, and

Fig. 6. CO₂-equivalents intensity, variation with different bauxite ore compositions.

so on. In this study, we have not considered accident risks and metals leaching from management of residual wastes, either P-BR or B-BR. As stated in Section 2.5, the comparison here excludes differences between the remaining residue and its management as the LCI modelling assumed identical management for both. Further, toxicity to humans and environment from metals leaching is not considered within our scope. However, it is known that the P-BR has lower alkalinity in comparison to B-BR, and thus we should expect the Pedersen process to offer benefits for the excluded impact categories compared to the Bayer process. These are priorities for local stakeholders to alumina plants and highly relevant for further evaluation of alumina production routes.

With coproduction of pig iron, the Pedersen process returns about half the mineral resource scarcity of the Bayer process, at the cost of doubling the energy demand and the volume of residual mineral waste. The tradeoff between solid waste to landfill, where Bayer would be preferred, and mineral resource scarcity, where Pedersen would be preferred, is interesting in light of the circular economy. Circular economy, energy and climate are important goals for a sustainable

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7. Endpoint results for damages to (a) Human health, (b) Ecosystems and (c) Resources, variation with ore compositions.

metallurgy. We have found that the preference for either process to climate change impacts depends on the carbon intensity of energy and ore grade, and our interpretation is that the ongoing energy transition benefits the Pedersen process and will eventually lead to its preference for climate change emissions. The preference in indicators for resource efficiency, waste and energy show more robust conclusions, with

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Relative midpoint indicator results for comparisons of Bayer and Pedersen process and different bauxite ore grades, with (a) European electricity inventory and (b) Norwegian electricity inventory. Scores are presented relatively to the highest value for each indicator among the five bauxites.

preference falling either way independent of changes in ore grade and energy supply.

It would be interesting to perform a wider scenario analysis to see the sensitivity to this comparison depending on expected changes in technologies, including alternative production and future transition in production routes for inputs factors. The Pedersen process could, for example, be used to process bauxite residue from the Bayer process, since the raw material can be considered as a high iron containing ore (Lazou et al., 2021). Or else, the use of hydrogen reduction instead of coke in the Pedersen process (Lazou et al., 2020), or novel routes for production of leaching agents (Wu et al., 2019). While beyond the scope of this paper, these would be relevant for more robust policy recommendations.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yan Ma: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Athina Preveniou:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Anastasios Kladis:** Writing – review & editing. **Johan Berg Pettersen:** Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- Agency, E.E., 2019a. EMEP/EEA Air Pollutant Emission Inventory Guidebook 2019 1. A.2Manufacturing Industries and Construction (Combustion).
- Agency, E.E., 2019b. EMEP/EEA Air Pollutant Emission Inventory Guidebook 2019 . 2. C.1 Iron and Steel Production 2019.
- Althaus, H.J., Hischier, R., Doka, G., Bauer, C., Dones, R., Nemecek, T., Hellweg, S., Humbert, S., Margni, M., Koellner, T., Loerincik, Y., 2007. Implementation of life cycle impact assessment methods Data v20 (2007) Ecoinvent report No 3. Switzerland, p. 151.
- Aluminium, W., 2015. Bauxite Residue Management: Best Practice.
- Aluminium, W., 2020. Alumina production. <http://www.world-aluminium.org/statistics/alumina-production/>.
- Association, E.A., 2013. Environmental Profile Report for the European Aluminium Industry.
- Azof, F.I., Safarian, J., Kolbeinsen, L., 2017. The Leachability of Calcium Aluminate Phases in Slags for the Extraction of Alumina.
- Azof, F.I., Vafeias, M., Panias, D., Safarian, J., 2020. The leachability of a ternary CaO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂ slag produced from smelting-reduction of low-grade bauxite for alumina recovery. *Hydrometallurgy* 191, 105184.
- Azof, F.I., Yang, Y., Panias, D., Kolbeinsen, L., Safarian, J., 2019. Leaching characteristics and mechanism of the synthetic calcium-aluminate slags for alumina recovery. *Hydrometallurgy* 185, 273–290.
- Balomenos, E., Panias, D., Paspaliaris, I., 2011. Energy and exergy analysis of the primary aluminum production processes: a review on current and future sustainability. *Miner. Process. Extr. Metall. Rev.* 32 (2), 69–89.
- Barbhuiya, S.A., Basheer, P.A.M., Clark, M.W., Rankin, G.L.B., 2011. Effects of seawater-neutralised bauxite refinery residue on properties of concrete. *Cement Concr. Compos.* 33 (6), 668–679.
- Bartie, N.J., Abadías Llamas, A., Heibeck, M., Fröhling, M., Volkova, O., Reuter, M.A., 2020. The simulation-based analysis of the resource efficiency of the circular economy – the enabling role of metallurgical infrastructure. *Miner. Process. Extr. Metall. (IMM Trans. Sect. C)* 129 (2), 229–249.
- Blake, H.E., United, S., Bureau of, M., 1967. Adaptation of the Pedersen Process to the Ferruginous Bauxites of the Pacific Northwest. U.S. Department of the Interior, Bureau of Mines, [Washington, D.C.
- Borra, C.R., Blanpain, B., Pontikes, Y., Binnemans, K., Van Gerven, T., 2016. Smelting of bauxite residue (red mud) in view of iron and selective rare earths recovery. *J. Sustain. Metall.* 2 (1), 28–37.
- Brouwer, F., Avgerinopoulos, G., Fazekas, D., Laspidou, C., Mercure, J.-F., Pollitt, H., Ramos, E.P., Howells, M., 2018. Energy modelling and the Nexus concept. *Energy Strategy Rev.* 19, 1–6.
- Burke, I.T., Mayes, W.M., Peacock, C.L., Brown, A.P., Jarvis, A.P., Gruiz, K., 2012. Speciation of arsenic, chromium, and vanadium in red mud samples from the Ajka Spill site, Hungary. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 46 (6), 3085–3092.
- Commission, E., 2019. In: Commission, E. (Ed.), COMMUNICATION from the COMMISSION to the EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, the EUROPEAN COUNCIL, the COUNCIL, the EUROPEAN ECONOMIC and SOCIAL COMMITTEE and the COMMITTEE of the REGIONS, the European Green Deal. Brussels.
- Committee, T.C.M.S.C.N., 2016. The Clay Minerals Society Glossary for Clay Science Project.
- Del Borghi, A., Moreschi, L., Gallo, M., 2020. Circular economy approach to reduce water-energy–food nexus. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sci. Health* 13, 23–28.
- Elomaa, H., Sinisalo, P., Rintala, L., Aromaa, J., Lundström, M., 2020. Process simulation and gate-to-gate life cycle assessment of hydrometallurgical refractory gold concentrate processing. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 25 (3), 456–477.
- Evans, K., 2015. Successes and Challenges in the Management and Use of Bauxite Residue, Bauxite Residue Valorisation and Best Practices. Leuven, Belgium, pp. 53–60.
- Evans, K., 2016. The history, challenges, and new developments in the management and use of bauxite residue. *J. Sustain. Metall.* 2 (4), 316–331.
- Factsage, 2020. Factsage 8.
- Gediga, J., 2014. Appendix 3 - life-cycle assessment. In: Worrell, E., Reuter, M.A. (Eds.), *Handbook of Recycling*. Elsevier, Boston, pp. 555–562.
- Hanssen, S.V., Huijbregts, M.A.J., 2019. Assessing the environmental benefits of utilising residual flows. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 150, 104433.
- He, J., Jie, Y., Zhang, J., Yu, Y., Zhang, G., 2013. Synthesis and characterization of red mud and rice husk ash-based geopolymer composites. *Cement Concr. Compos.* 37, 108–118.
- Hyeok-Jung, K., Kang, S.-P., Choe, G.-C., 2018. Effect of red mud content on strength and efflorescence in pavement using alkali-activated slag cement. *Int. J. Concr. Struct. Mater.* 12 (1), 18.
- INNOVA, E., 2012. Guide to Resource Efficiency in Manufacturing: Experiences from Improving Resource Efficiency in Manufacturing Companies.
- Jones, B.E.H., Haynes, R.J., 2011. Bauxite processing residue: a critical review of its formation, properties, storage, and revegetation. *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 41 (3), 271–315.
- Klauber, C., Gräfe, M., Power, G., 2009. Review of Bauxite Residue “Re-use” Options.
- Klett, C., Reeb, B., Missalla, M., Schmidt, H.-W., 2016. Methods to reduce operating costs in circulating fluidized bed calcination. In: Lindsay, S.J. (Ed.), *Light Metals 2011*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 125–130.
- Keith Hudson, L., Misra, Chanakya, Anthony, J., Perrotta, Wefers, Karl, Williams, F.S., 2000. Aluminum Oxide, Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry.
- Laskou, M., Economou-Eliopoulos, M., Mitsis, I., 2010. Bauxite ore as an energy source for bacteria driving iron-leaching and bio-mineralization. *Hell. J. Geosci.* 45, 163–174.
- Lazou, A., van der Eijk, C., Balomenos, E., Kolbeinsen, L., Safarian, J., 2020. On the direct reduction phenomena of bauxite ore using H₂ gas in a fixed bed reactor. *J. Sustain. Metall.* 6 (2), 227–238.
- Lazou, A., Van Der Eijk, C., Tang, K., Balomenos, E., Kolbeinsen, L., Safarian, J., 2021. The utilization of bauxite residue with a calcite-rich bauxite ore in the Pedersen process for iron and alumina extraction. *Metall. Mater. Trans. B* 52, 1255–1266.
- Liu, W., Chen, X., Li, W., Yu, Y., Yan, K., 2014. Environmental assessment, management and utilization of red mud in China. *J. Clean. Prod.* 84, 606–610.
- Liu, W., Yang, J., Xiao, B., 2009. Review on treatment and utilization of bauxite residues in China. *Int. J. Miner. Process.* 93 (3), 220–231.
- Ma, S.-h., Wen, Z.-g., Chen, J.-n., Zheng, S.-l., 2009. An environmentally friendly design for low-grade diasporic-bauxite processing. *Miner. Eng.* 22 (9), 793–798.
- Magagna, D., Hidalgo González, I., Bidoglio, G., Peteves, S., Adamovic, M., Bisselink, B., De Felice, M., De Roo, A., Dorati, C., Ganora, D., Medarac, H., Pistocchi, A., V.D. B., W., V. D., 2019. Water-Energy Nexus in Europe. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Miller, J., Irgens, A., 2016. Alumina production by the Pedersen process — history and future. In: Donaldson, D., Raahauge, B.E. (Eds.), *Essential Readings in Light Metals: Volume 1 Alumina and Bauxite*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 977–982.
- Mwase, J.M., Safarian, J., 2020. Investigating the Leaching, Desilication and Precipitation of Aluminium Tri-hydroxides from a Bauxite Residue-Bauxite By-Product Slag, the International Committee for Study of Bauxite. *Alumina & Aluminium*. ICOSBA 2020.
- Oberle, B., Bringezu, S., Hatfield-Dodds, S., Hellweg, S., Schandl, H., Clement, J., Cabernard, L., Che, N., Chen, D., Droz-Georget, H., Ekins, P., Fischer-Kowalski, M., Flörke, M., Frank, S., Froemelt, A., Geschke, A., Haupt, M., Havlik, P., Hüfner, R., Lenzen, M., Lieber, M., Liu, B., Lu, Y., Lutter, S., Mehr, J., Miatto, A., Newth, D., Oberschelp, C., Obersteiner, M., Pfister, S., Piccoli, E., Schaldach, R., Schüngel, J., Sonderegger, T., Sudheshwar, A., Tanikawa, H., van der Voet, E., Walker, C., West, J., Wang, Z., Zhu, B., 2019. IRP (2019). *Global Resources Outlook 2019: Natural Resources for the Future We Want*. A Report of the International Resource Panel. United Nations Environment Programme.
- Obersteiner, G., Binner, E., Mostbauer, P., Salhofer, S., 2007. Landfill modelling in LCA – a contribution based on empirical data. *Waste Manag.* 27 (8), S58–S74.
- Odenthal, H.-J., Kemminger, A., Krause, F., Sankowski, L., Uebber, N., Vogl, N., 2018. Review on modelling and simulation of the electric arc furnace (EAF). *Steel Res. Int.* 89 (1), 1700098.
- Pan, X., Yu, H., Tu, G., 2015. Reduction of alkalinity in bauxite residue during Bayer digestion in high-ferrite diasporic bauxite. *Hydrometallurgy* 151, 98–106.
- Patterson, S.H., 1967. In: Bulletin, - (Ed.), *Bauxite Reserves and Potential Aluminum Resources of the World*.
- Pauliuk, S., 2018. Critical appraisal of the circular economy standard BS 8001:2017 and a dashboard of quantitative system indicators for its implementation in organizations. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 129, 81–92.
- Pedersen, H., S.p., 1927. In: office, U. (Ed.), *Process of Manufacturing Aluminum Hydroxide*.
- Petersen, B., Bach, M., Arpe, R., 2016. The world's largest hydrate Pan filter: engineering improvements and experiences. In: Donaldson, D., Raahauge, B.E. (Eds.), *Essential Readings in Light Metals: Volume 1 Alumina and Bauxite*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 625–629.
- Petrakis, E., Bartzas, G., Komnitsas, K., 2020. Grinding behavior and potential beneficiation options of bauxite ores. *Minerals* 10 (4), 314.
- production, E.E.A.A.L., 2019. EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2019 2.A.2 Lime production 2019.
- Reuter, M.A., 2016. Digitalizing the circular economy. *Metall. Mater. Trans. B* 47 (6), 3194–3220.
- Reuter, M.A., Schaik, A.v., Ballester, M., 2018. Limits of the circular economy: fairphone modular design pushing the limits. *World Metall. Erzm. Metall.* 71 (2), 68–79.
- Reuter, M.A., van Schaik, A., 2015. Product-centric simulation-based design for recycling: case of LED lamp recycling. *J. Sustain. Metall.* 1 (1), 4–28.
- Reuter, M.A., van Schaik, A., Gediga, J., 2015. Simulation-based design for resource efficiency of metal production and recycling systems: cases - copper production and recycling, e-waste (LED lamps) and nickel pig iron. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 20 (5), 671–693.

- Ruyters, S., Mertens, J., Vassilieva, E., Dehandschutter, B., Poffijn, A., Smolders, E., 2011. The red mud accident in Ajka (Hungary): plant toxicity and trace metal bioavailability in red mud contaminated soil. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 45 (4), 1616–1622.
- Safarian, J., Kolbeinsen, L., 2016a. Smelting-reduction of bauxite for sustainable alumina production, Sustainable Industrial Processing Summit and Exhibition, pp. 149–158.
- Safarian, J., Kolbeinsen, L., 2016b. Sustainability in alumina production from bauxite, Sustainable industrial processing summit and exhibition, pp. 75–81.
- Scandrett, H.F., 2016. Equations for calculating recovery of soluble values in a countercurrent decantation washing system. In: Donaldson, D., Raahauge, B.E. (Eds.), *Essential Readings in Light Metals: Volume 1 Alumina and Bauxite*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 879–884.
- Schandi, H., Fischer-Kowalski, M., West, J., Giljum, S., Dittrich, M., Eisenmenger, N., Geschke, A., Lieber, M., Wieland, H., Schaffartzik, A., Krausmann, F., Gierlinger, S., Hosking, K., Lenzen, M., Tanikawa, H., Miatto, A., Fishman, T., 2018. Global material flows and resource productivity: forty years of evidence. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 22 (4), 827–838.
- Scheidema, M., Reuter, M., Roine, A., 2016. Life cycle assessment of metallurgical processes based on physical flowsheet models. In: Kirchain, R.E., Blanpain, B., Meskers, C., Olivetti, E., Apelian, D., Howarter, J., Kvithyld, A., Mishra, B., Neelameggham, N.R., Spangenberg, J. (Eds.), *REWAS 2016: towards Materials Resource Sustainability*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 179–185.
- Simapro, 2020. Simapro Multi user version.
- Smith, P., 2009. The processing of high silica bauxites — review of existing and potential processes. *Hydrometallurgy* 98 (1), 162–176.
- software, O.H.C., 2020. Outotec HSC Chemistry software.
- Standardization, I.O.f., 2006a. ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework.
- Standardization, I.O.f., 2006b. ISO 14044:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework.
- Thomson, M.R., McLeod, H.M., 1949. Recovery of Alumina from Submarginal Bauxites. Bureau of Mines Rept of Invest 4528.
- Union, T.E.p.a.t.c.o.t.E., 2006. Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2006 on the management of waste from extractive industries and amending Directive 2004/35/EC.
- Vafeias, M., Marinos, D., Panias, D., Safarian, J., Van Der Eijk, C., Solhem, I., Balomenos, E., Ksiazek, M., Davris, P., 2018. From red to grey: revisiting the Pedersen process to achieve holistic bauxite ore utilisation, Proceedings of the 2nd International Bauxite Residue Valorisation and Best Practices Conference, pp. 111–117.
- Verma, A.S., Suri, N.M., Kant, S., 2017. Applications of bauxite residue: a mini-review. *Waste Manag. Res.* 35 (10), 999–1012.
- Wang, Y., Zhang, T.-a., Lyu, G., Guo, F., Zhang, W., Zhang, Y., 2018. Recovery of alkali and alumina from bauxite residue (red mud) and complete reuse of the treated residue. *J. Clean. Prod.* 188, 456–465.
- Wargalla, G., Brandt, W., 2016. Processing of diasporic bauxites. In: Donaldson, D., Raahauge, B.E. (Eds.), *Essential Readings in Light Metals: Volume 1 Alumina and Bauxite*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 393–401.
- Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., Weidema, B., 2016. The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 21 (9), 1218–1230.
- Wu, Y., Xie, H., Liu, T., Wang, Y., Wang, F., Gao, X., Liang, B., 2019. Soda ash production with low energy consumption using proton cyclod membrane electrolysis. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 58 (8), 3450–3458.
- Zarasvandi, A., Charchi, A., Carranza, E.J.M., Alizadeh, B., 2008. Karst bauxite deposits in the Zagros mountain Belt, Iran. *Ore Geol. Rev.* 34 (4), 521–532.
- Zhu, X., Jin, Q., Ye, Z., 2020. Life cycle environmental and economic assessment of alumina recovery from secondary aluminum dross in China. *J. Clean. Prod.* 277, 123291.